

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Discrepancy Between Self-Reported and Measured Body Mass Index: A Narrative Review Protocol on Direction, Magnitude, Determinants, and Implications for Epidemiological Research and Health Policy Making

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Abstract

Background: Body mass index (BMI), calculated from height and weight, remains the most widely used indicator for monitoring overweight and obesity in clinical and public health practice. Self-reported height and weight are frequently used in large-scale epidemiological surveys and surveillance systems due to their lower cost and greater feasibility. Evidence consistently shows that self-reported data are subject to systematic bias, with individuals tending to overestimate height and underestimate weight, resulting in underestimated BMI and, consequently, underestimated prevalence of overweight and obesity. The magnitude and determinants of this discrepancy remain inconsistently characterized across the literature.

Objective: This protocol describes a narrative review that aims to synthesize evidence on the direction and magnitude of the discrepancy between self-reported and measured BMI, identify the demographic, somatometric, and psychosocial factors influencing this discrepancy, evaluate proposed correction methods, and discuss implications for epidemiological research and public health policy.

Methods: A systematic search will be conducted in PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar, supplemented by backward snowballing, following a PECO-structured framework. Eligible studies will include adolescents and adults reporting both self-reported and measured anthropometric values, or evaluating correction models. Screening will be performed independently by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved by a third reviewer. Findings will be synthesized thematically, without meta-analysis or formal quality appraisal, consistent with the narrative review design and SANRA guidelines.

Conclusions: The review is expected to provide an integrated account of reporting bias patterns, their determinants, and correction strategies, supporting more accurate epidemiological estimates and informing obesity-related public health policy.

Keywords: Self-reported height and weight; Body mass index (BMI); Measurement bias; Obesity surveillance; Anthropometric measurement; Reporting accuracy

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Introduction

Height and weight are two of the most fundamental anthropometric measurements used in clinical and public health practice, forming the basis of the body mass index (BMI). BMI is the most widely used indicator for monitoring overweight and obesity¹. Reliable body composition data is crucial for accurately tracking obesity and underweight burdens in populations. The preferred method for obtaining height and weight information is through direct measurement by trained professionals using calibrated tools. However, objective measurement is often costly and time-consuming, particularly in large-scale epidemiological surveys or surveillance studies where resources are limited^{2,3}. For this reason, many population health studies and national surveillance systems continue to rely on self-reported height and weight as a practical and cost-effective alternative.

The literature indicates that self-reported anthropometric data is regularly subject to systematic reporting bias⁴. Individuals tend to overestimate their height and underestimate their weight, a pattern observed across diverse populations⁵. As a result, BMI values calculated from self-reported data are typically lower than those derived from measured data, which can lead to an underestimation of the true prevalence of overweight and obesity in a population. The degree of misreporting also appears to be shaped by a range of sociodemographic and physical factors, including age, sex, BMI category, education level, race/ethnicity, and marital status, although findings across studies remain inconsistent⁶.

Older adults, for instance, are prone to overestimating their height, possibly because they continue to report height values recorded earlier in life, before age-related changes in bone and muscle structure reduced their actual stature⁷. Broader social and psychological factors, including heightened health awareness, the desire to appear socially acceptable, and the increasing acceptance of higher body weights in western cultures, have also been suggested as reasons for these reporting differences⁸.

The clinical and public health impacts of this bias are significant. BMI is widely used to classify individuals into weight categories and to estimate disease and mortality risk. Thus, systematic misreporting of height and weight can distort these classifications and, in turn, bias the observed associations between BMI and health outcomes such as cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and cancer⁹. Such inaccuracies ultimately compromise the planning, implementation, and evaluation of public health programs that rely on BMI-based data to monitor obesity trends and allocate resources⁵.

Although the validity of self-reported anthropometric data has been examined since at least 2007⁴, the evidence base has continued to evolve, and more recent studies offer an opportunity to reassess these patterns under contemporary conditions¹⁰. Given the persistent reliance on self-reported data in both research and surveillance contexts, and the inconsistencies that remain regarding the direction, magnitude, and determinants of reporting bias, there is a clear need to systematically synthesize the current evidence.

The present narrative review therefore aims to summarize and critically evaluate the comparative validity of self-reported versus measured height, weight, and BMI across clinical and epidemiological studies, and to identify practical strategies for improving the accuracy and reliability of self-reported anthropometric data collection.

Methods

Purpose and Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to investigate, through a narrative review of the literature, the discrepancy between self-reported and measured BMI. The specific research questions are as follows:

1. What is the direction (overestimation/underestimation) and magnitude of the discrepancy between self-reported and measured BMI?
2. Which demographic, somatometric, and psychosocial factors influence the magnitude and direction of this discrepancy (gender, age, actual BMI, educational level, race/ethnicity, geographic region, body image)?
3. What methods have been proposed to correct or mitigate this error (direct measurement, correction equations, adjustment by subgroups, statistical distribution correction models)?
4. What will be the implications of this bias for epidemiological research (prevalence estimates, association analyses, mortality studies) and for the formulation of public health policies?

To guide the search strategy and define the eligibility criteria, the research question was structured according to the PECO framework¹¹: Population — adults and adolescents without clinical conditions affecting body weight; Exposure — self-reported values of height, weight, or BMI; Comparator — objectively measured values of height, weight, or BMI by trained personnel; Outcome — the magnitude and direction of the

discrepancy between self-reported and measured values, as well as the factors that determine it.

Study Design

A narrative review design was selected because the purpose of this study is the thematic synthesis and interpretation of findings from heterogeneous populations, study designs, and measurement methods, rather than the quantitative aggregation of effect sizes. The narrative approach allows the integration of different types of studies (epidemiological studies, methodological comparisons, evaluations of corrective models) within a unified explanatory framework. This protocol and the subsequent narrative review have been designed in accordance with, and will adhere to, the SANRA guidelines¹².

Data Sources and Search Strategy

The literature search will be conducted in the online databases PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The search strategy will be structured around four thematic concepts: self-report (self-assessment); somatometric measures (Body Mass Index, BMI, height, weight, anthropometric measurements); accuracy/discrepancy (measured, validity, accuracy, agreement, bias, discrepancy, misclassification, under-report, over-report); and error correction (correction, adjustment, calibration, prediction equation, measurement error).

The search strategy in PubMed will be:

("Self Report"[Mesh] OR "self-report*" [tiab] OR "self-reported" [tiab] OR "self-assessment" [tiab]) AND ("Body Mass Index"[Mesh] OR "BMI" [tiab] OR "height" [tiab] OR "weight" [tiab] OR "anthropometric" [tiab]) AND ("measured" [tiab] OR "validity" [tiab] OR "accuracy" [tiab] OR "agreement" [tiab] OR "bias" [tiab] OR "discrepancy" [tiab] OR "misclassification" [tiab] OR "under-report*" [tiab] OR "over-report*" [tiab]) AND ("correction" [tiab] OR "adjustment" [tiab] OR "calibration" [tiab] OR "prediction equation" [tiab] OR "measurement error" [tiab])

The search strategy in Scopus will be:

TITLE-ABS-KEY(("self-report*" OR "self-reported" OR "self-assessment"))
AND
TITLE-ABS-KEY(("BMI" OR "body mass index" OR "height" OR "weight" OR "anthropometric"))
AND
TITLE-ABS-KEY(("measured" OR "validity" OR "accuracy" OR "agreement" OR "bias" OR "discrepancy" OR "misclassification" OR "under-report*" OR "over-report*"))
AND

TITLE-ABS-KEY(("correction" OR "adjustment" OR "calibration" OR "prediction equation" OR "measurement error"))

The search strategy on Google Scholar will be:

("self-reported" OR "self-report") AND ("BMI" OR "body mass index" OR height OR weight OR anthropometric) AND (measured OR validity OR accuracy OR agreement OR bias OR discrepancy OR misclassification) AND (correction OR adjustment OR calibration)

Filters will be applied based on the language of publication (only studies in English will be accepted) and the study population (studies involving humans). There will be no restrictions on the publication date or the type of study.

The search will be supplemented by a manual review of the reference lists of the articles deemed relevant, in order to identify additional studies not retrieved through the electronic searches (Backward Snowballing).

To ensure the currency and relevance of the evidence base, no fixed publication-year cutoff was imposed, but priority was given to studies published within the last 15 years, supplemented by earlier foundational or frequently-cited studies where they remain methodologically relevant (e.g., original validation studies or landmark reviews still cited as reference points in the field). Reference saturation was considered achieved once repeated backward snowballing from included studies ceased to yield new eligible sources. To avoid excessive self-citation, no more than a small proportion of references were drawn from any single author group or research team.

Eligibility criteria

Studies will be eligible for inclusion if they involved adult or adolescent populations, are published in English, and report both self-reported and measured values of weight, height, or BMI, or evaluate correction models or equations addressing self-report error. No restrictions were placed on geographic origin or year of publication. Studies will be excluded if they focus on clinical populations, such as individuals with eating disorders or chronic conditions affecting body weight, or if they lack a clear comparison between self-reported and measured values.

Paper Selection Process

The selection will be conducted in two stages (title/abstract screening and full-text review) by two independent reviewers, without the use of automated tools for file management and deduplication. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion and, if necessary, by a third/senior reviewer designated in advance.

No standardized methodological quality assessment tool (e.g., the Newcastle–Ottawa Scale) will apply, as this is not part of the scope of a narrative review. Similarly, no meta-analysis or quantitative synthesis of effect sizes will be conducted.

Data Extraction

From each study that met the criteria, the following information will be extracted, where available:

- Year of publication, country/region where the study was conducted, sample size and characteristics
- Study design type (e.g., cross-sectional, prospective cohort, validation/methodological comparison study)
- Method of collecting self-reported data (e.g., questionnaire, telephone interview)
- Measurement method (protocol, equipment)
- Magnitude and direction of deviation (kg, cm, kg/m², kappa coefficients, r correlations)
- Factors examined as determinants of the deviation (gender, age, BMI, education, race/ethnicity, geographic region, body image)
- Any proposed correction models/equations and their performance

Synthesis and Presentation of Findings

Findings will be organized thematically into sections that mirror the review's research questions: the direction and magnitude of the discrepancy; its determinants (sex, age, actual BMI, educational/socioeconomic status, race/ethnicity/geography, and psychosocial factors); available methods for correcting the error; and its implications for epidemiological research and health policy. The synthesis will rely on qualitative comparison of findings across studies, drawing out both consistent patterns and points of divergence or contradiction in the literature.

Methodological limitations

Several limitations of this review should be acknowledged. As a narrative rather than systematic review, this approach does not permit quantitative pooling of findings or formal statistical testing of heterogeneity across studies. The absence of a standardized quality appraisal tool introduces the possibility of selection bias in how studies are identified, weighted, and discussed. The exclusion of non-English-language studies may have led to the omission of relevant evidence published in other languages, introducing a degree of language bias. Finally, considerable heterogeneity across studies in terms of study populations, measurement instruments, and the metrics used to express discrepancy (kg, cm, kg/m², kappa coefficients, correlation coefficients) limits the extent to

which findings can be directly compared across the included literature.

Ethical Issues

Ethical approval is not required for this review, as it draws exclusively on already published literature and does not involve the collection of primary data from human participants. All data used in the synthesis originate from previously published studies and contain no personal or sensitive information. The review nonetheless adheres to principles of responsible scholarship in the use and presentation of published data, including accurate and complete citation of all sources, careful avoidance of excessive self-citation, and consistent respect for the original authors' work, so as to ensure transparency and accuracy throughout the review process.

Conclusion

This narrative review is expected to offer a critical, integrated account of the systematic discrepancy between self-reported and measured BMI, highlighting its key demographic and psychosocial determinants alongside available correction methods. By synthesizing this evidence, the review aims to support greater epidemiological accuracy in studies relying on self-reported anthropometric data and to inform more reliable public health policy, particularly in obesity monitoring, resource allocation, and intervention evaluation.

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